

THE ROLE OF PODCASTS TO ENHANCE STUDENT'S LISTENING SKILLS

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Annotation Using a podcast as multimedia can be useful as a tool for listening skills. Students and teachers can take podcasts as listening material and use them widely within the subject. Podcast material used for listening comprehension provides students with authentic and contextual material. Podcasts offer an ideal medium for the creative creation of preferred learning by students and provide a fun way for students and teachers to learn listening content or material. Podcasts, in particular, increase students' interest in listening to the English language, making it easy and convenient to learn the language of the country being studied. The purpose and objectives of this scientific article is to highlight the importance of providing students with podcasts as listening materials to improve students' listening skills.

Key words- communication, podcast, listening materials, language proficiency,

"bottom-up" method, discourse, content, contex, listening skill, extensive listening, intensive listening.

Аннотация Использование подкаста в качестве мультимедиа может быть полезным инструментом для развития навыков аудирования. Учащиеся и преподаватели могут использовать подкасты в качестве материала для прослушивания и широко использовать их в рамках предмета. Материал подкаста, используемый для понимания на слух, предоставляет учащимся аутентичный и контекстуальный материал. Подкасты предлагают учащимся идеальную среду для творческого создания предпочтительных учебных материалов и предоставляют учащимся и преподавателям интересный способ

изучения контента или материалов для прослушивания. Подкасты, в частности, повышают интерес учащихся к прослушиванию английского языка, позволяя легко и удобно изучать язык изучаемой страны. Цель и задачи этой научной статьи — подчеркнуть важность предоставления студентам подкастов в качестве материалов для прослушивания для улучшения навыков слушания.

Ключевые слова: общение, подкаст, материалы для прослушивания, владение языком, метод «снизу вверх», дискурс, содержание, контекст, умение слушать, экстенсивное слушание, интенсивное слушание.

Annotatsiya Podkastdan multimedia sifatida foydalanish tinglash qobiliyatini oshirish vositasi sifatida foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Talabalar va o'qituvchilar podkastlarni tinglash materialli sifatida olishlari va ulardan mavzu doirasida keng foydalanishlari mumkin. Tinglab tushunish uchun foydalaniladigan podkast materiallari talabalarga haqiqiy va kontekstli materiallarni taqdim etadi. Podkastlar talabalar tomonidan afzal ko'rgan o'rganishni ijodiy yaratish uchun ideal vositani taklif qiladi va talabalar va o'qituvchilar uchun tinglash mazmuni yoki materialini o'rganishning qiziqarli usulini taqdim etadi. Ayniqsa, podkastlar o'quvchilarning ingliz tilini tinglashga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirib, o'rganilayotgan davlat tilini oson va qulay o'rganish imkonini beradi. Ushbu ilmiy maqolaning maqsadi va vazifalari talabalarning tinglash qobiliyatini oshirish uchun podkastlarni tinglash materiallari sifatida taqdim etish muhimligini ta'kidlashdir.

Kalit so'zlar - aloqa, podkast, tinglash materiallari, tilni bilish, "pastdan yuqoriga" usuli, nutq, mazmun, kontekst, tinglash qobiliyati, keng tinglash, intensiv tinglash.

Listening plays an important role in everyday communication, and this has been shown in real life with the following figures: adults spend 40-50% of their communication time for listening, 25-30% for speaking, 11-16% reading, and

about 9% for writing¹. Listening is the most common language skill that is often used alongside other speaking, reading and writing skills. It is not only an area of skill in language performance, but also an excellent means of acquiring a second and foreign language. In language learning, listening has gone through several important stages, from being "acquired through exposure but not really taught"² to "a primary tool for language learning"³. In recent years, developments in education, linguistics, and sociology have led to an active interest in strong theories of the nature of language comprehension and the role of listening comprehension in second language acquisition.

If the listening material is appropriate for the level of the students, it is a very important point and serves as an effective tool. At the same time, extensive listening should go hand in hand with intensive listening. Extensive listening, in which the teacher encourages students to choose what they listen to for enjoyment or for general language improvement, can also have a significant impact on student language proficiency⁴. Using appropriate multimedia in extensive listening activities can be one of the solutions to increase students' listening ability and motivation⁵. Using multimedia, students can not only hear the sound but also see the visual, and with the multimedia, the students can download the existing sounds as a source of their listening material. One important application that can be used is a podcast. Using podcasts, students can listen to music, news, TV shows, and more. The podcast stores files in two different formats: two audio (MP3) and video (MP4) files. Listening material provided through a podcast can increase students'

¹ Vandergrift. 1999. Facilitating Second Language Listening Comprehension: Acquiring Successful Strategies. <http://docutec.Canberra.edu.au/cours> epage

² Richards, J.C. 2002. Listening Comprehension: Approach, Design, Procedure. *ESOL Quarterly*, 17 (2): 29- 240

³ Rost, M. 2002. *Teaching and Researching Listening*. London: Pearson Education.

⁴ Harmer, J. 2001. *The Practice of English Language Teaching* (3rd Edition). Harlow: Longman

⁵ Juniardi, Y. 2008. Improving Students Listening Skill through Podcasting Program. Paper presented in Asia TEFL Conference Bali, 23rd August.

listening comprehension⁶ because Podcasts provide students with authentic and contextual material, and it can improve student learning because students can share their Podcasts. Podcasts offer an ideal medium for creative expression of knowledge preferred by today's students and provide a fun way for students and teachers to learn and discover listening content or material⁷. Podcasts are audio or video files that are automatically streamed over a network and then played on any Mac, PC, or iPod. When students create a podcast for the classroom, they not only learn content in a creative way, but they also learn communication skills while experiencing the language of the country being studied and how it is expressed in society.

Clearly, language learning depends on listening because it provides the audio input that serves as the basis for language acquisition and serves as a realistic model for students to communicate in oral communication. Listening is the first language that all humans acquire, that is, they learn by listening from birth. It forms the basis for all aspects of language and cognitive development and plays a key role in communication processes. Listening, according to Wang Shouyuan, is the most important component of the five aspects of general English competence that he proposed, such as listening, speaking, reading, writing and translating, so it deserves special attention. Teachers should actively study the nature and process of listening comprehension and study the theory and methodology of listening comprehension, so as to improve the results of listening teaching and make students realize that listening comprehension is a crucial aspect of English learning. From the point of view of linguistics, foreign language teaching should pay attention to the form and meaning of the language, so the teaching of listening is carried out in the important aspects of the language form. When teaching students to understand a passage of text, teachers first allow them to distinguish the

⁶ Yumarnamto. 2008. Podcasts and Videocasts from the Internet to Improve Students' Listening Skill. Paper presented in Asia TEFL Conference Bali, 1st-3 rd August.

⁷ McCarty, S. 2005. Spoken Internet To Go: Popularization through Podcasting. JALT CALL, 1(2), 67-74.

pronunciation of sounds, and then to understand vocabulary, sentences and discourse. The "bottom-up" of this model of listening instruction is to help understand the meaning of vocabulary through sounds, to monitor and control the meaning of discourses by understanding the meaning of sentences and understanding the meaning of sentences. In terms of language tasks, teaching listening is not just about getting students to hear sounds, words, or sentences, but instead, the goal is to develop students' communication skills and understanding speakers' intentions⁸. Contrary to the theory that listening is a passive activity, it is important to realize that listening is a complex process involving many factors. Rost states that "listening is a process that involves a continuum of active processes that are under the listener's control." It differs from hearing, which is "the primary physiological system that allows the listener to receive and transform the sound waves that surround him"⁹. Thus, a complete definition of listening should include at least four factors: receptive, constructive, collaborative, or transformative¹⁰. Receptive means receiving what the speaker says, while constructive means constructing and expressing meaning. Collaborative implies negotiating meaning with the speaker, while transformative requires creating meaning through engagement and imagination. Generally speaking, effective listening involves the listener's active participation in the process of meaning with the speaker. In addition, effective listening is interactive because the meaning of the conversation is monitored and discussed¹¹.

Teaching listening using podcasts can increase students' listening comprehension because podcasts provide students with authentic and contextual

⁸ Lee, B. 2007. Podcasts Transforming Campus Life. The Monterey County Herald.

⁹ Rost, M. 2002. Teaching and Researching Listening. London: Pearson Education.

¹⁰ Rost, M. 2002. Teaching and Researching Listening. London: Pearson Education.

¹¹ Rost, M. 2002. Teaching and Researching Listening. London: Pearson Education.

material, and it can improve students' learning because they share their podcasts¹². Podcasting is an ideal medium for creative expression of knowledge preferred by today's students and provides a fun way for students and teachers to learn and discover listening content or material. Podcasting allows teachers to take their students beyond the traditional learning process by allowing them to add audio recordings, photos, movies, and sound effects to share their knowledge¹³. For example, students may develop scripts as a writing assignment, create a visual progress report for an ongoing project, or submit a written version of a science presentation¹⁴. Podcasting is also a great way for teachers to deliver listening content to their students. ELT podcasts can be used for intensive and extensive listening activities, but ELT podcasts are ideal for extensive listening to stimulate students' interest in listening to English and expose them to the speech of native speakers¹⁵. As Stanley¹⁶ points out, podcasts provide students with ample opportunities for additional listening both in and out of the classroom: scripted and scripted listening means supplementing the textbook with real-life, authentic conversations that we can find in many podcasts. An attractive option for carefully selected language teachers, extracts can bring a variety of voices and English into the classroom. This activity is effective in teaching English as a second language as well as teaching English as a foreign language. The key to helping students improve their listening skills is to convince them to finish the work. It's more of an attitude adjustment than anything else, and it's easier for some students to accept than others. Another important point is that teachers should convince their students

¹² Earp, S. 1998. More Than Just the Internet: Technology for Language Teaching. ERIC Digest <http://www.ericdigests.org/1998-2/internet.htm>

¹³ Yumarnamto. 2008. Podcasts and Videocasts from the Internet to Improve Students' Listening Skill. Paper presented in Asia TEFL Conference Bali, 1st-3rd August.

¹⁴ Stoks, G. 2005. Podcasts: New Materials for Teaching Listening Comprehension. Retrieved from www.babylonia.ch: 26 April 2006.

¹⁵ Rost, M. 1991. Listening in Action: Activities for Developing Listening in Language Teaching. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

¹⁶ Stanley, G. 2006. Podcasting: Audio on the Internet Comes of Age. TESL-EJ, 9(4).

to listen to English as often as possible. With regard to listening material, the more material they are exposed to, the more successful¹⁷.

In conclusion, it is known that for students learning English as a foreign language, there is usually a gap between hearing sounds and understanding words, phrases and sentences. Such intervals often lead to more difficulty in listening comprehension for students. Therefore, it is very important that they have more contact with different listening materials and familiarize their ears with the different sounds of English words. In classroom activities, teachers can give some tips to students to improve their listening skill; one of the useful suggestions is extensive listening. The best resource for comprehensive listening is a well-chosen podcast material. In addition, intensive and comprehensive listening activities using podcasts are able to develop students' listening skills and meet their need for extra time to improve their listening skills.

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